

Modeling Dipolar Nonprotogenic Solvents with PC-SAFT-Type Equations of State: Pure Substance Properties

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Abstract

Dipolar nonprotogenic solvents (DNSs) are interesting and important substances widely used in various applications, including organic syntheses, sustainable fuels, or organic electronics. They exhibit intriguing molecular and interactional properties, characterized by large dipole moments, strong dipole–dipole interactions, hydrogen bond (HB) acceptor ability, and the formation of dimer complexes. The latter aspect, along with the traditional view of DNSs as having a weak or negligible HB donor ability, has led to debates about the origin (dipolar *vs.* HB) of these complexes. Therefore, modeling and predicting the thermodynamic properties of DNSs is challenging and requires sophisticated approaches. The PC-SAFT-type equations of state are powerful tools for describing the macroscopic thermodynamic properties of fluid systems, including DNSs. In this work, we explore and compare the performance of various modeling strategies within PC-SAFT for pure DNSs, including nonpolar, explicitly dipolar, and pseudo-associating approaches. These strategies differ in the treatment of the strongly dipolar character of DNSs. The PC-SAFT parameter sets for each DNS and strategy were determined *de novo* by fitting them to reliable reference data on the liquid density and vapor pressure. A comprehensive computational evaluation of the results for the fluid-phase thermodynamic properties of six DNSs in their pure form is provided, and the merits and drawbacks of the considered strategies are discussed. The pure-compound parameter values are also analyzed. The best results are obtained from the pseudo-association strategy, which considers DNSs to be self-associating with both HB acceptor and donor sites, followed by an explicitly dipolar approach with optimized dipole moment values. Surprisingly, a nonpolar strategy without any explicit dipolar treatment provides results comparable to those of the above models. It is also demonstrated that optimized or gas-phase dipole moments of DNSs are significantly better for use within PC-SAFT in the context of pure DNSs than those related to the liquid phase calculated quantum-mechanically using a polarizable continuum model.

Keywords

PC-SAFT equation of state; dipolar nonprotogenic solvents; solvent media; molecular interactions; thermodynamic properties; parametrization

1 Introduction

Dipolar nonprotogenic solvents (DNSs; or dipolar aprotic solvents¹), such as acetonitrile, *N,N*-dimethylformamide, γ -valerolactone, or sulfolane, are important class of chemical substances. They possess a strongly dipolar character, characterized by a large permanent dipole moment. For example, acetonitrile and γ -valerolactone exhibit gas-phase dipole moment values of 3.9 D and 4.7 D, respectively, which is more than double the dipole moment of water (1.85 D).² However, they are typically considered to lack sufficiently labile (acidic) hydrogen atoms to act as hydrogen bond donors.¹

The pronounced dipolar character of DNSs is anticipated to significantly influence the macroscopic thermodynamic properties of both pure DNSs and their mixtures with other substances. DNSs exhibit several intriguing physicochemical properties, including a high relative permittivity, low volatility, high boiling point, and favorable miscibility and solubilization behavior.³⁻⁶ Specifically, they are typically completely miscible with water, alcohols, and other DNSs, while they show a limited miscibility with, for example, *n*-alkanes.⁷⁻¹³

DNSs are used in a broad spectrum of applications. For example, they include renewable green solvents derived from biomass,^{12,14-16} sustainable energy sources,^{5,9} precursors for other chemicals, reaction media for organic synthesis,^{17,18} or efficient green solvents for the fabrication and processing of organic semiconductors,¹⁹⁻²³ for example, in the context of organic photovoltaics and thin-film transistors.

For high-throughput screening of solvents for organic molecules or to evaluate whether a DNS is a suitable solvent for a given application, knowledge and description of its thermodynamic behavior are crucial. State-of-the-art predictive thermodynamic models for phase equilibria in mixtures, such as modified UNIFAC²⁴ or COSMO-type models,^{25,26} cannot provide a pressure dependence of thermodynamic properties or predict properties of pure substances like the liquid density, vaporization properties, and heat capacity, which are important for a complete picture of the thermodynamic behavior. (However, in the case of COSMO-type models, additional treatments have been proposed to enable the prediction of

some of these properties^{27,28}). This highlights the importance of equations of state (EOS), which provide comprehensive thermodynamic information on both mixtures and pure substances. The statistical associating fluid theory (SAFT) EOSs, including the perturbed-chain SAFT (PC-SAFT)²⁹⁻³¹ as one of the most successful representatives, are rooted in a solid theory based on statistical thermodynamics.³²⁻³⁴ They can explicitly (at least qualitatively) account for various types of interactions, including both dipolar and association interactions that play a crucial role in systems containing DNSs (see the discussion below). The association interactions usually, but not necessarily, refer to hydrogen bonding (HB). Therefore, these advanced EOSs are used to model the thermodynamic properties of a broad spectrum of chemical systems, including complex substances with intricate interactional and structural characteristics, such as, for example, pharmaceuticals,^{35,36} ionic liquids,^{37,38} and polymers.^{39,40} The literature on the application of PC-SAFT to *mixtures* containing DNSs is vast (*e.g.*, refs⁴¹⁻⁴⁵), while specific applications to the properties of *pure* DNSs are less frequent.^{31,46-48}

To choose an appropriate modeling strategy for DNSs that adequately accounts for their molecular properties and intermolecular interactions, a deeper understanding of these important factors is essential. Figure 1 shows the molecular structures and electrostatic potential maps of three exemplary DNSs: γ -valerolactone (GVL), propylene carbonate (PC), and acetonitrile (ACN). Molecules of DNSs exhibit a substantial hot spot of increased electron density corresponding to lone electron pairs in electronegative atoms (O, N, or S). Taking GVL as an example, its hot spot is given by the close proximity of carbonyl and alkoxy oxygen atoms, where an increased electron density is concentrated, which also results in its high HB acceptor ability (specifically, the double-bonded carbonyl oxygen is reported to be the dominant HB acceptor site⁴⁹⁻⁵¹). Because DNS molecules typically feature only one such hot spot and the rest of the molecular surface generally exhibits a lower charge density, these permanent asymmetries in their electron distributions are responsible for their large permanent dipole moments.

Figure 1: Molecular structures and electrostatic potential maps of some exemplary DNSs (calculated quantum-mechanically in Gaussian 16 software⁵² at the MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory). From left to right: γ -valerolactone, propylene carbonate, and acetonitrile. The red and blue regions represent negative and positive charges, respectively.

With regard to pure substances, the large dipole moments entail strong dipole–dipole interactions between DNS molecules, leading to significant molecular ordering in the liquid phase and even the formation of DNS \cdots DNS dimer complexes. This phenomenon has been demonstrated, for example, by Aparicio and Alcalde,⁷ Richardi *et al.*,⁵³ and Knözinger and Wittenbeck⁵⁴ for GVL, ACN, and acetone, respectively. They also revealed that these dimers preferentially have an out-of-plane arrangement with an antiparallel (head-to-tail) orientation of the molecular dipoles. However, Świergiel *et al.*⁵⁵ later found the parallel in-plane arrangement to be the most favorable mutual configuration of GVL and PC molecules in their liquid-phase complexes, on the basis of static permittivity measurements. Nevertheless, these and other^{51,56–58} studies clearly indicate the existence of strong dipolar interactions between DNS molecules and their tendency to aggregate in the liquid phase, which influences the macroscopic thermodynamic behavior of pure DNSs. The important long-range dipole–dipole interactions can explicitly be taken into account in PC-SAFT through a dipolar contribution^{31,46,59} (see Section 2.1).

The tendency of DNS molecules to form aggregates raises questions about the presence of specific short-range HB interactions in their pure form, in addition to dipole–dipole interactions, despite not apparently having HB donor ability.⁶⁰ (Such HB interactions could be described by the association contribution of PC-SAFT.) Interestingly, the results of respec-

tive studies in the literature can be both in favor and against the existence of HB between DNS molecules, depending on individual DNSs, conditions, and research means (experimental or computational). For example, Aparicio and Alcalde,⁷ using both experimental and computational techniques, have dismissed the existence of HB interactions between molecules of GVL both in out-of-plane and in-plane dimer arrangements. They found that the GVL dimer complexes and their properties (*e.g.*, interaction energy and bond distance) did not meet the criteria for being considered to originate from HB interactions. As a result, the complexes are assumed to have a dipolar nature.^{7,55} This would suggest that DNS molecules are not self-associative in the traditional sense of HB, mainly because they lack HB donor sites in form of a protic hydrogen atom, which is also supported by their Kamlet–Taft solvatochromic parameters.⁶⁰ However, for the GVL–ethanol system, Mbaiwa and Nyepetsi⁵¹ recently showed through computational means [classical molecular dynamics and quantum mechanics (QM)] that unconventional (GVL)C–H···O(ethanol) HB interactions also play an important role. This finding indicates that GVL exhibits at least a weak HB *donor* ability, which could also manifest in its pure form.

In analogy to GVL, the complexation behavior of acetone (which is similar to that of ACN⁵⁴) is predominantly attributed to dipolar interactions by some researchers,^{54,57} while others ascribe it to HB interactions,^{58,61} or a combination of both,⁶² as recently discussed by NguyenHuynh *et al.*⁴⁵ The latter option appears reasonable because HB interactions, as a chemical concept, result from a combined effect of multiple physical forces including electrostatics (*e.g.*, dipole–dipole interactions), charge-transfer, induction, and dispersions.⁶³

Therefore, it may not be completely clear whether or not the association term should be employed when modeling the properties of pure DNSs with PC-SAFT. This is mainly because their HB donor ability may not be necessarily negligible, as indicated in refs^{51,58,61,62}. However, it is worth noting that this term was originally designed to describe molecular associations in a general sense, not exclusively HB interactions.³² Therefore, describing the formation of DNS···DNS complexes using the association term would sound quite mean-

ingful regardless of the question of whether the physical interaction is of the dipolar or HB origin. This idea was explored by von Solms *et al.*,⁶⁴ who treated polar molecules, including acetone, as self-associating using the simplified PC-SAFT EOS⁶⁵ without incorporating any dipolar term. This "pseudo-association" approach was later tested also by other authors^{45,66,67} and typically yielded improved results for both pure compounds and mixtures, compared to the completely nonself-association approach with respect to DNSs. Such results are encouraging, regardless of whether the pseudo-association concept has or lacks a physical justification. However, modeling DNSs as polar but nonself-associating remains the prevailing strategy within the PC-SAFT framework.^{10,11,31,41–44,47,48,59,68} This highlights the need for further investigation in this area.^{45,66}

For completeness, although the ability of DNSs to form HB between themselves is ambiguous, it is quite clear that they can participate in cross-HB interactions in mixtures with molecules possessing HB donor sites, such as alcohols and water. Therein, DNSs act as HB acceptors due to their lone electron pairs. In the case of γ -valerolactone, these induced cross-associations (often termed solvation) were confirmed both spectroscopically^{49,50} and computationally.⁵¹ These important effects can also be taken into account using the association term of PC-SAFT.^{68,69} However, the cross-associations are not considered in this study, as it exclusively focuses on the properties of pure DNSs.

The interactional intricacies outlined above illustrate the challenges associated with proper modeling of DNSs and their properties. For thermodynamic models including SAFT EOSs, the selection of a modeling and parametrization strategy generally impacts the outcomes regarding both pure components and mixture properties. Our previous studies on the performance of various PC-SAFT-type models for DNSs, including GVL¹⁰ and dihydrolevoglucosenone,¹³ interestingly indicated a somewhat ambiguous effect of the explicit inclusion of the high dipole moment (specified by experiment or QM calculation). While it appears to be essential for a reasonable description of some properties [*e.g.*, liquid–liquid equilibria (LLE) in mixtures with hydrocarbons], it has a negative impact on the model

accuracy for other properties (*e.g.*, heat capacity of a pure DNS). Therefore, the goal of the current work is to explore and compare the performance of various modeling strategies within the PC-SAFT EOS for pure DNSs in more detail, including nonpolar, explicitly dipolar, and pseudo-associating approaches. To this end, a broader set of six different DNSs and four pure-compound properties are considered. Specifically, the six DNSs are: GVL (CAS: 108-29-2), PC (CAS: 108-32-7), ACN (CAS: 75-05-8), dihydrolevoglucosenone (DLG; CAS: 53716-82-8), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP; CAS: 872-50-4), and sulfolane (SUL; CAS: 126-33-0). Regarding applications, ACN, NMP, and SUL are conventional "nongreen" DNSs, while GVL, PC, and DLG represent novel and sustainable alternatives.^{12,14,15,18,70} The pure-compound properties include the liquid density (ρ^{liq}), vapor pressure (p^{sat}), enthalpy of vaporization (Δh_{vap}), and residual isobaric liquid heat capacity (c_p^{res} ; *i.e.*, the difference between the isobaric heat capacity of liquid and ideal gas). Based on a comprehensive computational evaluation of the results for the fluid-phase thermodynamic properties of pure DNSs, the merits and drawbacks of the considered strategies are discussed, also in the context of the values of dipole moments and other pure-compound parameters.

The next section describes the computational details and the PC-SAFT modeling strategies considered. The results obtained are then presented and analyzed in Section 3. Finally, the observations are summarized and contextualized in the last section.

2 Computational Methods

2.1 PC-SAFT EOS and Its Configurations

the performance of various modeling approaches (nonpolar, dipolar, pseudo-associating) to model pure DNSs within PC-SAFT. Based on a comprehensive computational evaluation of the results for the fluid-phase thermodynamic properties of pure DNSs, the merits and drawbacks of the strategies are identified.

PC-SAFT views molecules as chains composed of spherical segments that can interact with each other. It calculates the residual Helmholtz energy, a^{res} (*i.e.*, the difference between the Helmholtz energy of a real fluid system and that of an ideal gas), by summing individual contributions reflecting the structural and interactional characteristics of the chains (molecules):²⁹⁻³¹

$$a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}} + a^{\text{DD}} + a^{\text{assoc}} \quad (1)$$

In eq 1, the term a^{hc} includes repulsive interactions, closely related to the size of a molecular hard chains (hc), which are described by the number of spherical segments forming a chain (m) and their diameter (σ). The attractive dispersion interactions are described by the term a^{disp} and parametrized using compound-specific dispersion energy parameter (u/k_{B} ; k_{B} denotes the Boltzmann constant). The dipolar term a^{DD} accounts for the dipole-dipole interactions of permanent dipoles (μ). In this work, we employed the dipolar term proposed by Gross and Vrabec³¹ (GV). The GV dipolar contribution was derived using a third-order perturbation theory and assumes that the dipole moment is oriented axially to the molecular axis. This seems to match with the asymmetric electron distribution in molecules of DNSs, as shown in Figure 1. In the GV term, the integrals related to the correlation functions are approximated by power series in density whose coefficients were fitted to comprehensive molecular simulation data.³¹ Association interactions, such as hydrogen bonding, are explicitly accounted for through the term a^{assoc} , which is common to different SAFT versions. A detailed description of the contributions to a^{res} in eq 1 can be found in the original

papers.^{29–31,71} From a^{res} , other thermodynamic properties can be calculated, including those considered in this work.^{29,72}

However, the terms a^{DD} and a^{assoc} on the right-hand side of eq 1 are not always used. For nonpolar substances (with $\mu \rightarrow 0$), such as hydrocarbons, eq 1 reduces to $a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}}$. In this case, only three parameters per compound have to be known (m , σ , and u/k_{B}). For polar but nonself-associating substances including DNSs, it typically reads $a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}} + a^{\text{DD}}$. This model configuration is sometimes referred to as PCP-SAFT (PC polar SAFT)³¹ and requires the dipole moment in addition to m , σ , and u/k_{B} . For self-associating substances, such as water and alcohols, eq 1 is usually used in the form $a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}} + a^{\text{assoc}}$, *i.e.*, without the dipolar term. The simultaneous application of a^{DD} and a^{assoc} is rather scarce,^{68,73,74} since the latter term is expected to implicitly absorb the effects of dipole moments.^{75,76} a^{assoc} requires two additional parameters for an associating component to be known: the association energy ($\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$) and the effective association volume (κ^{assoc}). Furthermore, the so-called association scheme (N^{assoc}) must be specified, *i.e.*, the number of different association sites.

For most chemicals, including DNSs, the compound-specific parameters m , σ , u/k_{B} , and eventually $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$ and κ^{assoc} are usually determined by fitting them to experimental data on the properties of pure compounds, namely, ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} . The dipole moment μ can be adjusted (*e.g.*, fitted together with the other parameters), or specified before the parameter optimization procedure.³¹ In the latter case, experiment- or QM-based dipole moments can be used.

2.2 PC-SAFT Modeling Strategies and Parametrizations Applied

In total, four different PC-SAFT modeling strategies (MS) were considered for each of the DNS. These strategies differed in the treatment of the strongly dipolar nature of DNSs. Specifically, the four MS were as follows:

MS1 A PC-SAFT model without a dipolar term that considers DNSs to be nonpolar and

nonself-associating (with $\mu = 0$ D, $a^{\text{DD}} = 0$, and $a^{\text{assoc}} = 0$). This model contains three adjusted parameters (m , σ , and u/k_{B}).

MS2 A PCP-SAFT model with the GV dipolar term explicitly considering a DNS to be dipolar but nonself-associating ($a^{\text{assoc}} = 0$), with a specified value of μ (calculated independently by QM with a polarizable continuum model) and with three adjusted parameters (m , σ , and u/k_{B}).

MS3 A PCP-SAFT model with the GV dipolar term explicitly considering a DNS to be dipolar but nonself-associating ($a^{\text{assoc}} = 0$), with μ being an adjustable parameter regressed together with m , σ , and u/k_{B} .

MS4 A PC-SAFT model without any dipolar term ($a^{\text{DD}} = 0$) but with the association term that considers a DNS to be self-associating with five adjustable parameters (m , σ , u/k_{B} , $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$, and κ^{HB}), thus reviving the "pseudo-association" concept proposed by von Solms *et al.*⁶⁴ The association scheme "2 (1, 1)" was used for all DNSs, which comprises a total of two association sites, one "positive" (*e.g.*, HB donor) and one "negative" (HB acceptor) site (it is also known as 2B association scheme⁷⁷).

Illustrations of a GVL molecule within the PC-SAFT hard-sphere representation for each MS are provided in Figure 2 (compare with the electrostatic potential map of GVL in Figure 1). The number of segments reflects the values obtained for the parameter m within each MS, as detailed in Table 2.

Figure 2: Molecular models of GVL in form of the hard-sphere representation inherent to the PC-SAFT-type EOSs for: (a) MS1, (b) MS2 and MS3, and (c) MS4. The arrow in (b) represents the dipole moment, which is restricted to stretch over two segments at most, according to the model theory.³¹ The small solid circles in (c) represent the association sites.

For each DNS, the sets of adjustable pure compound parameters for the four modeling strategies were identified by fitting them to the reference data on ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} . (MS1 and MS2 for DLG have already been presented in our recent contribution¹³). To ensure consistency and facilitate fair comparison, we used the same reference data for all four MSs for each DNS. The sources and temperature ranges of these reference data are provided in Table 1. In most cases, we did not use primary experimental data, but their correlations provided in the original papers (for example, using the Cox or Clarke–Glew equation for p^{sat}). Therefore, we call these reference data "pseudo-experimental". For p^{sat} , Δh_{vap} , and c_p^{res} , we preferred the consistent and recommended data sets produced by prof. Ružička and co-workers^{13,78–80} using the method of simultaneous correlation⁸¹ based on precise and critically assessed experimental data. The parameters were determined using the simulated annealing optimization method^{82,83} (as in our previous studies^{36,38,84}), which is a global optimization method that minimizes the possibility of being trapped at a local minimum. The objective function, which was minimized in the parameter optimization procedure, was used in the common form:

$$F_{\text{obj}} = \frac{1}{N_\rho} \sum_{i=1}^{N_\rho} \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{calc}}^{\text{liq}} - \rho_{\text{exp}}^{\text{liq}}}{\rho_{\text{exp}}^{\text{liq}}} \right)_i^2 + \frac{1}{N_p} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \left(\frac{p_{\text{calc}}^{\text{sat}} - p_{\text{exp}}^{\text{sat}}}{p_{\text{exp}}^{\text{sat}}} \right)_j^2 \quad (2)$$

In eq 2, N_ρ and N_p denote the number of pseudo-experimental data points for ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} , respectively. The subscripts "exp" and "calc" denote the pseudo-experimental data and those calculated with the PC-SAFT EOS, respectively. The parameter values obtained for MS1 to MS4 are provided in Table 2 and discussed in more detail in Section 3.1. For all calculations performed in this work with PC(P)-SAFT, including the parameter optimization, we utilized our in-house Fortran codes.

In the case of PS2, the dipole moment values were specified before the parameter regression. They were calculated in the Gaussian 16 software (revision C.01)⁵² at the MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory with Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM)⁹⁵ to emulate the condensed-phase state of pure DNS. These single-point calculations were performed at the optimal

Table 1: Reference data and their temperature range^a (in K) and sources

DNS	$(\rho^{\text{liq}})^{\text{b}}$	p^{sat}	Δh_{vap}	$(c_p^{\text{res}})^{\text{c}}$
GVL	288–453 ^{10,85}	240–480 ⁸⁰	240–480 ⁸⁰	265–358 ⁸⁰
PC	298–368 ⁸⁶	260–440 ⁸⁰	260–440 ⁸⁰	220–420 ⁸⁰
ACN	255–455 ⁸⁷	280–490 ⁸⁸	298 ⁸⁹	230–300 ^{90,91}
DLG ^{13,92}	293–353 ¹³	253–403 ¹³	253–403 ¹³	260–350 ¹³
NMP	298–373 ⁹³	265–525 ⁷⁹	260–520 ⁷⁹	265–355 ⁷⁹
SUL	303–373 ⁹³	300–530 ⁷⁸	300–530 ⁷⁸	305–355 ⁷⁸

^a The temperature ranges are significantly below the critical points of the compounds⁹⁴ except for ACN, whose maximum temperature of 490 K considered corresponds to $0.9 \cdot T_c$.

^b At $p = 0.1$ MPa, except for ACN, for which saturated ρ^{liq} were considered.

^c At $p = 0.1$ MPa. For all DNSs except ACN, the single source of c_p^{res} includes c_p for both the liquid and ideal gas phases. For ACN, c_p^{liq} was taken from ref⁹⁰, while that for the ideal gas from ref⁹¹.

molecular geometries determined using MP2/6-311++g(d,p). The use of PCM was motivated by the fact that the dipole moments of polar substances are higher in the bulk liquid phase than in the gas phase^{42,96} (the difference can typically reach 30–40%). The relative permittivities of the considered DNSs used in the PCM calculation are provided in Table S1 in the SI. For comparison purposes, we also calculated the gas-phase dipole moment values, at the same QM level but without PCM, and compared them with their experimental counterparts (also shown in Table S1). In the context of the formulation of a^{DD} , we consider all DNSs to contain a single polar group (with $n_\mu = 1$), allowing the use of molecular dipole moments (as usual for DNSs in the literature^{31,42,44,47}), instead of multiple group-based μ with $n_\mu > 1$.

It should be noted that the DNSs considered here has previously been parametrized within PC-SAFT in various studies,^{10,42,47,48,97,98} covering both nonpolar and polar regimes. However, we opted not to utilize these parametrizations mainly because they were determined using different reference data and temperature ranges, which could introduce inconsistency and bias into our comparison. Furthermore, the reference data used for these older parametrizations may now be outdated due to ongoing advancements in knowledge of the physicochemical properties of pure DNS.^{13,48,80}

3 Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the performance of the four modeling strategies within PC-SAFT for the pure-compound properties of the considered DNSs. The obtained results in terms of relative deviations (RD; see Table S2 for its definition) from the pseudo-experimental data as a function of temperature are shown in Figures S1 to S6 in the SI. The average absolute relative deviation (AARD; Table S2) values between the pseudo-experimental data and the data calculated with the considered strategies are displayed in Figure 4.

3.1 Pure-Compound Parameter Values

First, the values of the pure-compound parameters obtained for the considered DNSs within the four modeling strategies are inspected and discussed. These values are shown in Table 2.

For MS1, the obtained parameter values correspond to the values typically obtained for strongly polar DNSs within the nonpolar PC-SAFT treatment.^{10,31,47} These are characterized by quite high u/k_B values above approximately 330 K that numerically compensate the missing explicit treatment of the high dipole moments of DNSs. For comparison, u/k_B values for (cyclo)alkanes and esters are typically around 250 K.²⁹ In the case of SUL, the u/k_B parameter value reached even 430 K, but values above 390 K for SUL within a nonpolar treatment are not surprising,^{98,99} as they have to compensate for a significant dipole moment of SUL (see the following paragraph).

Regarding the explicitly polar MS2 approach, the corresponding PCM-based dipole moment values (μ^{PCM}) can be seen in Table S1. This table also shows that they are 23–40% higher than those in vacuum (μ^{gas}), and that some of them are quite high, such as those of PC and SUL that are above 7 D.

The inclusion of MS3 in this work allows for a comparison of the optimal μ values regressed to ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} data and μ values calculated theoretically using QM (both in PCM and vacuum). This comparison is shown in Figure 3 by means of a parity plot. For all DNSs,

Table 2: PC-SAFT parameters for the DNSs considered in this work

MS	m	$\sigma/\text{\AA}$	$(u/k_B)/\text{K}$	μ/D	$(\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B)/\text{K}$	κ^{assoc}	N^{assoc}
GVL							
MS1	3.0113	3.5713	353.04				
MS2	3.7811	3.3017	228.99	6.18 ^a			
MS3	3.0910	3.5413	326.21	3.8277			
MS4	4.1358	3.1392	210.31		1950.8	1.5926	2 (1, 1)
PC							
MS1	2.9036	3.5047	393.09				
MS2	4.2307	3.0888	178.14	7.35 ^a			
MS3	2.8832	3.5150	388.27	2.5470			
MS4	3.9319	3.1124	242.24		1952.8	1.5484	2 (1, 1)
ACN							
MS1	2.0730	3.2966	334.83				
MS2	2.9110	2.9590	114.37	4.85 ^a			
MS3	2.3101	3.1727	228.43	3.6763			
MS4	3.0340	2.7692	160.18		1697.5	1.7522	2 (1, 1)
DLG							
MS1 ^b	3.4155	3.5050	343.20				
MS2 ^b	3.8872	3.3565	270.99	5.55 ^a			
MS3	3.4176	3.5039	342.86	1.1430			
MS4	3.3663	3.5302	343.79		70.089	0.6356	2 (1, 1)
NMP							
MS1	3.1282	3.5304	344.03				
MS2	3.5511	3.3872	258.23	5.60 ^a			
MS3	3.1114	3.5419	331.47	3.3685			
MS4	3.1789	3.5274	325.76		224.25	1.5 ^c	2 (1, 1)
SUL							
MS1	2.8507	3.6755	430.54				
MS2	3.7219	3.3650	260.17	7.08 ^a			
MS3	2.8729	3.6722	412.74	3.5646			
MS4	3.0517	3.5824	333.71		1693.1	0.7408	2 (1, 1)

^a Specified before the parameter regression.

^b Taken from Jeřábek *et al.*¹³

^c Specified before the parameter regression because of extremely large and small values of κ^{assoc} and $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$, respectively (see the text).

the optimized dipole moments have values lower than those obtained from QM. However, for all six DNSs, the gas-phase dipole moments agree much better with the optimized values than those based on PCM. For ACN as an example, the μ^{opt} value of 3.7 D harmonizes well

Figure 3: Comparison of the dipole moments of the considered DNSs optimized to ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} data within MS3 (μ^{opt}) with those calculated using QM (μ^{QM}) in PCM (solid symbols) and vacuum (empty symbols).

with 3.9 D obtained from both QM/vacuum and experiment, as shown in Table S1. This indicates that the gas-phase μ values are a better alternative for DNSs to use within the PCP-SAFT framework, although the PCM-based μ should theoretically align more closely with the dipole moment values in the liquid phase. One of the rationalizations may consist in the fact that the antiparallel configuration of the DNS molecules in dimers in the liquid, in which the molecular dipoles are oppositely aligned, leads to a partial cancelation of the effects of the dipole moments,⁴⁷ thus lowering the average effective dipole moment. The best agreement between μ^{opt} and $\mu^{\text{QM,gas}}$ is found for ACN and NMP, while the poorest agreement is exerted by PC and, particularly, DLG. For the latter, μ^{opt} reached a very low value slightly above 1 D.

Therefore, we determined an additional set of PCP-SAFT parameters for each DNS using the μ^{gas} values. This fifth set is provided for potential users in Table S3, along with the corresponding statistical deviations. However, it is not further discussed in this paper, as its results fall between those of MS2 and MS3.

In the case of MS2 and MS3, the values of u/k_B are accordingly lower as a result of the application of a^{DD} that explicitly covers the effects of dipolar interactions. The decrease of u/k_B when switching from MS1 to MS2 or MS3 is roughly proportional to the dipole moment

values used in these "dipolar" strategies, as illustrated in Figure S7a. This also explains that the u/k_B values of MS2 are always lower than their MS3 counterparts because the PCM-based dipole moments in MS2 are generally greater than those obtained within MS3. The only outlying points in Figure S7a are those of ACN, which foreshadows somewhat tricky results for this DNS (see the following sections).

Regarding the pseudo-association MS4, the values of the association energy parameter $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$ for GVL, PC, ACN, and SUL obtained within MS4 reached 1700 K to 1950 K. These values appear reasonable because they are (i) between those typically found for, *e.g.*, 1-alkanols (2500–3000 K^{30,84}) and moderately polar compounds such as ethers (≈ 1000 K)^{64,66} and (ii) in agreement with those found for ketones when treated as self-associating (1300–1900).^{64,66} Furthermore, they are close to binding energies of acetone and GVL dimers reported in the literature (1620 K and 2300 K, respectively).^{7,61} These are some of the aspects that would justify the consideration of DNSs as self-associating.

However, the $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$ values obtained for DLG and NMP are extremely small and even lower than the corresponding values of u/k_B . This occasionally happens for DNSs^{64,98} as well as moderately polar substances, pharmaceuticals,³⁶ or other complex chemicals,¹⁰⁰ and suggests that MS4 is not an efficient choice in these cases, as it brings no improvement in the model performance compared to MS1 (as illustrated in the following sections) at the cost of two additional parameters to fit. An extreme situation in this regard was observed for NMP, for which the simulated annealing procedure tended to determine a too low $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$ value (below 50 K) and a very high κ^{assoc} value (above 7). To fix this, we reduce the number of regressed parameters from 5 to 4 by specifying the κ^{assoc} value to 1.5, which corresponds to those obtained for GVL, PC, and ACN within MS4 (see Table 2). This led to a more reasonable but still relatively low $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$ value of 224 K. (In the case of complex substances, fixing κ^{assoc} is quite normal and sometimes even inevitable to achieve reasonable parameter values.^{35,36,101}) For clarity, these low $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$ values do not negatively impact the accuracy of MS4, since this strategy provided excellent results for both DLG and

NMP, as discussed in the following sections.

In the case of DLG, the low $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$ value correlates with the low value of μ^{opt} obtained for this DNS within MS3, both diminishing the importance of a^{DD} or a^{assoc} in the MS3 and MS4 calculations, respectively. This also causes MS3 and MS4 to almost reduce to the nonpolar MS1, which is further evidenced by (i) the similar m , σ , and u/k_{B} values obtained for DLG within MS1, MS3, and MS4 (see Table 2) and (ii) the fact that the results of these three strategies form a "bundle" of close curves (see Figure S4). As a result, the explicit inclusion of dipolar or association interactions does not appear critical to capture the behavior of *pure* DLG. However, we recently showed that a^{DD} is crucial to achieve a reasonable description of LLE in mixtures of DLG with hydrocarbons.¹³ Furthermore, Figure S7b suggest that the mutual correlation between $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$ from MS4 and μ^{opt} from MS3 is not completely general. However, if the point for NMP (denoted with an exclamation mark) is excluded from the evaluation (because it was obtained with a fixed κ^{assoc}), the coefficient of determination, R^2 , of the remaining points reaches 0.73, indicating a relatively strong correlation.

3.2 Liquid Density

In the case of ρ^{liq} (and p^{sat}), it is *correlative* performance that is evaluated, as these data were used directly in the parameter fitting procedure through eq 2. Therefore, the model errors typically achieve low values for these two properties. As can be seen in Figure 4a, all modeling strategies excellently reproduce ρ^{liq} with AARD(ρ^{liq}) values below 0.6% for all considered DNSs except ACN. Taking into account the results for all six DNSs, the best results for ρ^{liq} were obtained with MS4, followed by MS3 and MS1, while the largest error was achieved by MS2. However, even the total AARD(ρ^{liq}) produced by MS2 does not exceed 1.6%, including the problematic results for ACN.

In some cases (*e.g.*, GVL and PC), the models exhibit a less accurate representation of the temperature dependence of ρ^{liq} , which is related to the isobaric thermal expansivity. As

a result, the absolute errors are highest at the edges of the considered T intervals and may potentially be even greater beyond these ranges.

For ACN, all modeling strategies except MS4 exert significantly higher $\text{AARD}(\rho^{\text{liq}})$ values than for the other DNSs. This can (at least partially) be attributed to the fact that the reference data on (saturated) ρ^{liq} of ACN covered a wide temperature interval up to the temperature corresponding to $0.83T_c$ (see Table 1), while the T intervals for the other DNSs were narrower and only up to $\approx 0.6T_c$ at most. Furthermore, Kleiner and Gross⁴⁷ also reported both nonpolar and polar PC-SAFT models to provide considerably higher $\text{AARD}(\rho^{\text{liq}})$ values (above 6%) for ACN than for the other DNSs. In particular, the AARD value for ρ^{liq} of ACN above 8% achieved by MS2 can be an extremely large error in the context of applications. Moreover, as shown in Figure S3, individual data points at temperatures above 400 K have even larger errors up to 30%. (This drastic increase in error with increasing T is also associated with the fact that MS2 predicts a substantially lower T_c value for ACN than the other strategies.) In contrast, the results for ρ^{liq} of ACN obtained from

Figure 4: AARD values obtained from PC-SAFT with the different modeling strategies for the considered pure-compound properties: (a) liquid density, (b) vapor pressure, (c) enthalpy of vaporization, and (d) residual isobaric liquid heat capacity. Figure (d) displays the total AARD calculated over all four properties.

MS4 are excellent.

The overall accuracy of the MSs for ρ^{liq} is in the following order: MS2 < MS1 < MS3 < MS4. However, as Figure 4a reveals, the differences among them are numerically quite small (except for those of ACN). This order appears to correlate with the number of adjustable parameters (*i.e.*, 3, 3, 4, and 5, respectively) and, thus, with the flexibility of the respective MS. It is surprising that MS1, the PC-SAFT model that neglects any explicit treatment of the large dipole moments of DNSs, outperforms the "polar" MS2 with its fixed μ from QM.

3.3 Vapor Pressure

Next, we focus on the ability of the MSs to reproduce the vapor pressure data. For p^{sat} , the strategies qualitatively follow the same "behavioral" pattern as for the liquid density. Specifically, the accuracy again increases in the order MS2 < MS1 < MS3 < MS4. The highest AARDs are again observed for ACN. All strategies except MS2 give AARD(p^{sat}) values below 1 %, even for ACN. This can be considered as excellent, as such small errors are not always obtained even for less polar substances.^{29,31} Moreover, it appears that even individual data points in the considered temperature ranges do not exceed RD values of 1 % or 2 %, as can be seen in Figures S1 to S6.

In contrast, MS2 provided the less accurate representations of p^{sat} . The corresponding AARDs reach 2 % to 9 %, with the latter observed, not surprisingly, for ACN. Figure S3 shows that this high deviation value is mainly caused by data points at temperatures below 350 K, where the corresponding RDs reach even -20 %. This is also associated with incorrectly capturing the temperature dependence of p^{sat} , indicating that the MS3 model, with the high PCM-based dipole moment, is not as flexible as the other strategies.

3.4 Enthalpy of Vaporization

The enthalpy of vaporization is considered as an additional indicator of the quality of the PC-SAFT performance for the considered DNSs. Although Δh_{vap} was not explicitly used

in the parameter regression, it is generally interrelated with p^{sat} through the Clapeyron equation (Δh_{vap} relates to the T -dependence of p^{sat}). Therefore, if an EOS represents p^{sat} and its temperature course well, it should theoretically provide a reasonable Δh_{vap} as well.

The AARD(Δh_{vap}) values obtained from the four MSs are shown in Figure 4c. For all DNSs except ACN, the strategies MS1, MS3, and MS4 provided excellent results with AARDs below 0.6% (these low errors also hold for individual data points at the whole T -range; see Figures S1 to S6). Furthermore, these three MSs provided completely comparable results, slightly blurring the dominance of MS4.

MS2 achieved an overall error of 2%. An inspection of Figures S1 to S6 reveals that the data points at the edges of the temperature intervals contribute the most to the resulting AARD values of MS2, while the smallest RD(Δh_{vap}) values are found in the temperature interval of approximately 300–350 K. This is a consequence of the "diagonal" shape of RD(Δh_{vap}), showing the largest negative errors at lower temperatures and the largest positive errors at higher temperatures. This behavior corresponds to the U-shaped temperature dependence of AARD(p^{sat}). MS2 was surpassed not only by MS3 (with optimized μ) but also by the completely nonpolar MS1. Therefore, it appears that the μ values obtained from the PCM calculation are too high to be used in the context of PC-SAFT. This is most visible in the case of ACN, for which MS2 gives very poor correlations of both ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} . As a result, when applying a dipolar PC-SAFT model to DNSs with dipole moments obtained from an independent external source, the ideal-gas values of μ appear to be a significantly better choice than those from PCM.

MS4 is the only model that describes ρ^{liq} , p^{sat} , and Δh_{vap} of ACN with a good accuracy comparable to those obtained for the other DNSs. A technical explanation is that a model with at least five adjustable parameters (MS4) is needed to reasonably model both ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} of ACN simultaneously. The physical explanation is that only the pseudo-association concept can correctly capture the interaction behavior of pure ACN, as also indicated by other studies.^{45,64} Finally, all models generally show a slight tendency to overestimate Δh_{vap} ,

especially at higher temperatures.

3.5 Residual Isobaric Liquid Heat Capacity

The (residual) heat capacity is an important thermodynamic parameter of fluids in the context of heat-transfer processes. At the same time, it is a thermodynamic response function, *i.e.*, a second-order derivative of the Helmholtz energy which measures the reaction of the fluid to changes in temperature.

The overall $\text{AARD}(c_p^{\text{res}})$ values for the considered DNSs are displayed in Figure 4d. At first sight, it is obvious that $\text{AARD}(c_p^{\text{res}})$ values obtained from the four PC-SAFT models are generally much higher than those achieved for the other properties. However, this situation is normal, since c_p^{res} is, as a response function, very sensitive to model formulation and parameterization. Therefore, EOS, including cubic and SAFT-type ones, are known to have difficulties to correctly capture c_p^{res} , as demonstrated in previous studies.^{72,84,102}

The relative performance of the modeling strategies for c_p^{res} is: $\text{MS2} < \text{MS3} < \text{MS4} < \text{MS1}$. This means that the nonpolar MS1 outperformed MS4 this time (specifically, for 5 of the 6 DNSs), although the numerical differences between them are small, in most cases. The total $\text{AARD}(c_p^{\text{res}})$ values calculated over all six DNSs were about 5 % for both MS1 and MS4,

Figure 5: Values of c_p^{res} calculated by the MSs (at 300 K and 0.1 MPa) in comparison with their experimental counterparts.

which can be considered as excellent, in the context of somewhat higher error values typically observed for this derivative property. The most impressive MS1 and MS4 estimations of c_p^{res} are seen for GVL, PC, and SUL (Figures S1, S2, and S6, respectively). Furthermore, both MS1 and MS4 correctly describe the temperature dependence of c_p^{res} , as the respective curves in Figures S1–S6 are almost parallel to the horizontal axis in most cases. This is not always the case when modeling this quantity with EOSs. The superiority of MS1 and MS4 for c_p^{res} can further be demonstrated by qualitative results. Figure 5 shows that they provide a more correct order of the considered DNSs with respect to their c_p^{res} values than the other strategies.

Compared to MS2, the strategy with optimized μ values (MS3) dramatically improves the performance of PC-SAFT for c_p^{res} . However, MS3 generally does not provide better c_p^{res} estimations than MS1. This can be surprising, as the former has extra flexibility in the form of the fourth adjustable parameter (μ) and a^{DD} .

In general, the applied strategies show a tendency to underestimate c_p^{res} data. This is most visible in the case of MS2, whose individual errors can reach very large values, for example, around -100% for PC and ACN (see Figures S2 and S3, respectively).

For completeness, an improved description of c_p^{res} can generally be achieved, for example, by including a second-order derivative property, such as the speed of sound or c_p^{res} itself, in the objective function (eq 2) for parameter regression.¹⁰³

4 Concluding Remarks

In this work, four different modeling strategies within PC-SAFT for six DNSs were analyzed. They allowed evaluating and comparing the modeling results obtained (i) without the explicit inclusion of any dipolar interactions, (ii) with the explicit inclusion of them *via* the dipolar term, and (iii) by mapping the dipolar interactions using the association contribution. The pure-compound parameter sets were regressed in this work *de novo* (Tables 2 and S3) using updated and critically evaluated experiment-based data; therefore, they are recommended for further use within the PC-SAFT framework.

The nonpolar MS1 provided, in most cases, results comparable to those of MS3 and MS4, although it did not consider the strong dipolar effects explicitly. MS1 also clearly outperformed MS2 with its specified QM/PCM-based dipole moments. Although this has already been observed in the case of DLG,¹³ the general validity of this behavior also for the other DNSs can be surprising because explicitly capturing the large condensed-phase dipole moments of DNSs in a modeling framework for pure DNSs would otherwise appear reasonable. This is even more remarkable when taking into account that MS1 has (like MS2) the smallest number of adjustable parameters (three) among the considered strategies.

The polar MS2 produced the worst results, indicating that the PCM-based μ values are too high for use within the PC-SAFT and, in general, that the μ value should be treated carefully in this context. The question of which μ values are more appropriate has two principal answers. It appears that μ values optimized (MS3) together with the other parameters are generally the best choice (at the cost of introducing an additional regressed parameter). However, if a specified μ value from an external source is sought, *gas-phase* dipole moments, either from experiment or QM, appear to be a reasonable choice.

In the case of MS3, it can be argued that, rather than the explicit dipolar treatment itself, it is the presence of the fourth adjustable parameter that flexibilizes the model, leads to a better accuracy and makes the essential difference between MS3 and MS2 and MS1. However, MS3 sometimes produced slightly worse results than MS1, especially for the properties not

explicitly considered in the parameter regression (Δh_{vap} and c_p^{res}). Therefore, the number of *adjustable* parameters does not always appear to be the key factor.

The pseudo-association MS4 (five adjustable parameters) proved to be the winning strategy, as it provided the best overall results. The question of whether DNSs can technically be treated as self-associating within PC-SAFT is therefore positive, regardless of whether this representation is physically correct or not. This supports the considerations on the "absorption"/mapping of dipolar interactions in a^{assoc} . It also aligns with the original purpose of a^{assoc} itself, which was to describe associative interactions in general. Furthermore, the pseudo-association interactions in DNSs are not necessarily "pseudo", as documented by the large body of literature on the significant association behavior of DNSs (after all, the term "associations" is commonly used in the context of interactional behavior of pure DNSs, whether it refers to the dipolar or HB origin of these interactions). For DLG and NMP, MS4 does not provide significant benefits over MS1 or MS3, as a result of the small values of the association parameters. This observation aligns with general considerations⁶⁴ that the association of DNSs is not a binary question (existing/nonexisting) but rather a question of intensity or degree, in the context of which different DNSs can behave differently. Finally, MS4 involves the greatest number of fitted parameters, which makes the minimal experimental dataset required in the fitting procedure larger than for the other strategies.¹⁰⁴ However, $\varepsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$ can be specified using QM- or experiment-based binding energies of the DNS...DNS associates, since the values obtained within MS4 were in most cases comparable to those expected theoretically.

Despite all the individual details discussed, it should not be overlooked that PC-SAFT, particularly with MS3 and MS4, enables a very relevant representation of the properties of DNSs in their pure fluid. However, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the performance of various PC-SAFT modeling strategies for DNSs, it is imperative to consider not only their pure-substance properties but also their behavior in mixtures with other compounds. Exploring such mixtures will be the focus of our upcoming research.

Associated Content

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at [url].

- Dipole moment values calculated for the considered DNSs
- AARD values of the properties of the pure DNSs calculated with the four PC-SAFT modeling strategies from their pseudoexperimental counterparts
- Temperature course of the respective relative deviations
- PC-SAFT parameters for the DNSs considering the additional modeling strategy with gas-phase dipole moments
- Correlation between the dispersion and association energy parameters and dipole moments (PDF)

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Modeling Dipolar Nonprotogenic Solvents with PC-SAFT-Type Equations of State: Pure Substance Properties

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